

Research Symposium: Syria in Transition: Reconstructing State, Society, and Sovereignty

Introduction by Rana B. Khoury and Sefa Secen

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The fall of Bashar al-Asad in December 2024 marked a historic rupture in Syria's modern history. After more than thirteen years of revolution and civil war, the country now faces the immense task of reconstruction. Yet as the contributions in this symposium make clear, rebuilding Syria is not only about bricks and mortar. It is a profoundly political process, entangled with questions of sovereignty, state-society relations, displacement, social hierarchy, and justice. The very meaning of "reconstruction" remains unsettled: will it foster durable institutions and social trust, or merely reproduce coercion, exclusion, and dependency under new guises?

These critical questions are being posed in a highly unfavorable context. For half a cent-

ury, Hafiz al-Asad and then his son Bashar invoked methods of violent and hegemonic authoritarian rule that forbade dissent and eroded ties between Syrians and between Syria and the outside world. Since the 1990s, they also pulled back the socialist policies that had supported the well-being of ordinary Syrians; the middle class retreated with the state, even as the elite enriched themselves. When faced with a popular movement amid the wave of "Arab Spring" uprisings in 2011, the regime unleashed force rather than reform and initiated one of the most brutal wars of the twenty-first century. In the war's course, hundreds of thousands perished, millions were displaced, territory was fragmented, infrastructure crumbled, sanctions strangled, extremists thrived, and external

aactors had their way with the pieces.

It is difficult to fathom how peace and prosperity can possibly follow, even as Syrians desperately hope for and deserve better.

As particular as these challenges appear to be for Syria, our contributors have all reminded us that political science has dealt with similar questions before. Embedding their analyses in existing literature on post-conflict processes, democratization, forced migration, transitional justice, and international intervention, they help us anticipate the challenges—and possibilities—ahead.

One recurring theme is the struggle to re-imagine the relationship between rulers and ruled. Tiina Hyyppä emphasizes that while Asad's fall raised hopes for a new social contract based on trust, the interim government has at times leaned on coercive practices that echo the authoritarian past. Violence in Sweida and the exclusionary drafting of a transitional constitution illustrate how fragile the foundations of trust remain. This echoes Salam Said's description and analysis of the transitional leadership under Ahmed al-Sharaa. Her contribution shows that promises of inclusivity are belied by exclusive institution-building in politics, society, and the economy. The Syrian state, as such, is at stake.

The external dimension of reconstruction is equally fraught. Sumaya Malas traces how Bashar al-Asad's survival was propped up by foreign patrons who traded military and political backing for slices of Syria's economy. She warns that the new wave of Gulf investment carries similar risks: if reconstruction contracts are captured by elites and foreign partners rather than routed through transparent institutions, Syria may once again sacrifice sovereignty for short-term stability.

This theme of fragility is also evident in Sefa Secen's contribution, which interrogates return movements in the process of transition. He discusses how returns are uneven, fragile, and often temporary, reflecting localized security conditions and shifting host-state pressures. Counting returns, he argues, is not a straightforward sign of stability but a window into the churn of displacement and remigration that will likely define Syria's future.

Reconstruction is also reshaping Syria's social fabric in ways that risk entrenching new hierarchies. Ammar Shamaileh highlights how revolutionary legitimacy may be producing a privileged class with connections to the ruling elite and state resources, forged through wartime residence and revolutionary participation. Emily Scott, in turn, situates these dynamics within broader questions of justice and accountability and considers the international and local actors that may be involved in post-conflict processes. She cautions that without genuine transitional justice and survivor-led accountability, reconstruction will remain hollow and peace elusive.

These contributions reveal the challenges of Syria's transition. They also highlight pathways forward: rebuilding trust, reclaiming sovereignty, creating inclusive institutions, and centering justice. By foregrounding these perspectives, this symposium aims to spark scholarly and policy conversations about what reconstruction in Syria means and for whom. As the country enters this new chapter, the stakes could not be higher: whether Syrians will inherit another brittle and fierce order or lay the foundation for a more just and inclusive future. ♦